

Validation of Homeopathic Therapeutics in Iron Deficiency Anaemia of Female in Pubertal to Menopausal Age Group an Observational Study¹

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Abstract

Aim: To study the validation of experimentally proved homoeopathic medicines by the method of human pharmacology in cases of Iron deficiency anaemia, in females from puberty to menopause.

Study Design: It is an observational study.

Research Question: How homoeopathic therapeutic is validate in iron deficiency anaemia?

Material and Methods: This observational OPD based study was performed in Antarbharti Homoeopathic medical college and Martandya Homoeo clinic OPD between January 2022 to November 2024. Fifty women of age group 15 to 49, who manifested with general clinical conditions of anaemia were thoroughly evaluated.. The study parameters include patients haemoglobin concentration, serum iron concentration, serum ferritin level, serum transferrin saturatio. Diagnosis was based on cut off points, which is adult female Hb is 12gm/dl and MCHC 34%. Data was collected as per homoeopathic case taking proforma and was analyzed. Repertorization was done with the aid of Zomoeo software by totality of symptoms indicating a peculiar remedy for the individual case.

Inclusion

1. Female within age group of 15 to 49 were included in study.
2. Female who had given consent were included in study.

Exclusion

1. Females with haemoglobinopathies were excluded.

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- 2 Females who denied consent was excluded.
- 3 Females with other co-morbidity were excluded.
- 4 Pregnant women were excluded.

Result: Total fifty cases were screened for the study, out of which thirty showed Signs of iron deficiency anaemia with the aid of diagnostic tools and Pathogonomic symptoms.

Conclusion: In this study women with iron deficiency anaemia among pubertal and menopausal age group showed beneficial effect with proved homoeopathic medicines when prescribed according to the homoeopathic principles.

Keywords

Homoeopathic Therapeutics, Individualization, Iron Deficiency Anaemia, Totality of Symptoms.

Introduction

Iron is one of the essential trace element require for women in thriving. The omnivores mostly not affected with the deficiencies, but individuals on vegan diet affect with deficiencies because of the phytic acid and plenty of fibre. The adult female iron requirement as per WHO Expert group is about 12 gm/dl and MCHC is 34. [Park] This trace nutrient sustains many vital functions in human like formation of haemoglobin, regulation of body temperature, muscle activity, brain development, catecholamine metabolism, oxygen transfer and cell respiration. Apart from dietetic requirement there are other anomalies which may lead to depletion of iron causing anaemia viz celiac disease, tropical sprue. These gastric derangement hampers absorption. The supplementary elements which affect iron absorption are presence of inhibitors and promoters. The inhibitors are phosphate and the promoters are ascorbic acid. One of the determinant which also include is iron loss in women is through haemorrhage specially during menstruation, IUDs insertion, childbirth or pathological conditions and basal loss is through urine, sweat, bile and desquamation of cells. Haem-iron is better absorbed than non-haem iron. Haem iron is well supplied in liver, meat, poultry and fish seemingly non-haem iron is present in cereals, green leafy vegetables, legumes, nuts, oil seeds, jaggary and dried fruits.

Iron deficiency anaemia is a global health concern affecting children, women and the elderly, whilst also being a common comorbidity in multiple medical conditions. The aetiology is variable and attributed to several risk factors decreasing iron intake and absorption or increasing demand and loss, with multiple etiologies often coexisting in an individual patient. Although presenting symptoms may be nonspecific, there is emerging evidence on the detrimental effects of iron deficiency anaemia on clinical outcomes across several medical conditions. Increased awareness about the consequences and prevalence of iron deficiency anaemia can aid early detection and management. Diagnosis can be easily made by measurement of haemoglobin and serum ferritin levels, whilst in chronic inflammatory conditions, diagnosis may be more challenging and necessitates consideration of higher serum ferritin thresholds and evaluation of transferrin saturation.[1]

Anaemia affects roughly a third of the world's population; half the cases are due to iron deficiency[2] Specifically the pubertal to menopausal age group of women are more at risk for anaemia due to socio-economic, nutrition, functional and psychological factors. The approximate prevalence rate in generative age is 50 to 70 percent.

Iron Deficiency Anaemia Homoeopathic Point of View

Homoeopathy is based on the law of similia similibus Curantur and individualization after collecting the data from patient for erecting totality of symptoms, the cause and effect relationship is considered while treating the patient. Analysis was based according to Dr Kent's methodology focusing on emotional modality of will and affections, which assumed highest significance followed by physical generals and characteristic particulars. The therapeutic methodology was applied as per indications. After the approach of terminating presenting complaints care was also taken to eradicate the complete abnormal susceptibility with constitutional treatment to avoid proneness to recurrence. The circumstances which impede inferior resistance like deficiencies or excess of dietic errors was rectified with proper guidance.

Reportorial Chart

Figure -1

Figure -2

Kali carb: Indicated in fleshy aged people having tendency to dropsy. Giving out sensations. Early morning aggravation associated with sweat, backache and weakness.[Dr.Boericke] It affects blood and circulation causing anemia and haemorrhage. There is peculiar sensation as if the heart were suspended by thread.[Murphy]

Sulphur: Nutrition is affected on account of defective assimilation, the patient emaciates. When carefully selected remedy fails to act. It causes irregular circulation, causing burning, throbbing or congestion.[Murphy]

Carbo Veg: Anaemia due to loss of blood. Body become blue icy cold, Deficient capillary circulation causes blueness of skin and coldness of extremities, vital powers nearly exhausted, desire to be constantly fanned. [Murphy]

China: Indicated after climacteric with profuse haemorrhage.excessive lactation, diarrhoea, acute disease often result in dropsy.Obligated to move limbs frequently, as motion gives relief. Anaemia and dropsy.[Murphy]

Adjuvant Supplement

Understanding iron metabolism is pivotal in the successful management of ID and iron deficiency anaemia (IDA) using oral preparations, parenteral iron or blood transfusion.[3].

We also have to rule out causa occasionalis which may serve as an obstacle in the cure. Supplementation of diet like Lentils, beans, tofu, fortified cereals, spinach, red meat, poultry, fish and organ meat like liver is recommended. Iron rich supplementation should be coupled with vitamin C supplementation for simple absorption.

Results and Observation

Table no: 1 Result as Per Age Group

SN	AGE	NO OF CASES	% OF CASES
01	15-18	17	56.66%
02	19-30	10	33.33%
03	31-49	03	0.1%

Table no: 2

SN	AETIOLOGY	AGE GROUP	NO OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE
01	NUTRITIONAL DEFICIENCIES	15 -30	18	0.60%
02	EMOTIONAL/PHYSICAL STRESS	25 -35	09	0.30%
03	HAEMORRHAGE	30 - 49	03	0.10%

Interpretation of result was carried out with the help of Z score scale which showed positive result after homoeopathic therapeutics in patients with iron deficiency anaemia.

Discussion:

Iron deficiency anaemia is most common in reproductive age group and it need a Wholistic approach. Patients with varied reproductive age group from puberty to menopause was considered in study. They

all were clinically diagnosed with Iron deficiency anaemia. Proper investigations were done at regular interval. Evaluation of the iron status of patient was done on parameters like, haemoglobin concentration, serum iron concentration, serum ferritin level and serum transferrin saturation. The indicated medicines were prescribed after case-taking and case processing followed by appropriate doses and follow-ups. All the ethical guideline was followed.

Conclusion:

This research on Validation of Homoeopathic therapeutics in Iron deficiency anaemia of female in pubertal to menopausal age group an observational study was completed. Homoeopathic therapeutics showed positive findings in the patients. Thus it shows that homoeopathic therapeutic is valid when applied according to its principles wholistically ruling out the obstacles in the way of cure. It is beneficial in rectifying the syndrome causing the functional disturbances like reduced resistance to infection, increased morbidity, diminished work performance, impaired cell mediated immunity. After the study the aim was achieved.

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Abbreviations

OPD - Out Door Patient Department.

MCHC - Mean Corpuscle Haemoglobin Concentration,

ID -Iron Deficiency,

IDA- Iron Deficiency Anaemia,

WHO - World Health Organization.